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ENHANCING PERMEABILITY OF ACYCLOVIR BY LIPOSOMAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Liposomes are derived from Greek word lipo means fat and soma means body, composition of phospholipids these are made up of phospholipids bi layer, encapsulated in both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs and safe guard from degradation these formulations due to its biodegradable and biocompatible characteristics, many drug delivery applications have been fully examined over the last decade. Acyclovir is BCS Class III drug with low permeability. To enhance the permeability of acyclovir drug by liposomal drug delivery system by thin film lipid hydration by hand shake method. Acyclovir liposomes are penetrated to biological membrane and enhance their pharmacological action and drug release. Enhance the rate of drug permeability is enhanced there by increases the Bioavailability of poorly BCS class III drug – Acyclovir and improved therapeutic efficacy and compliance of the patient. Recent trends so many students and research scholars desire and significance will increase for this technology mainly because of wide range of therapeutic applications in targeting delivery of several enzymes' antibiotics anti virals, anti-parasite transdermal transports and diagnostic tools and vaccines. The goal of topical liposome delivery approaches is to get access by combining different polymers.

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INTRODUCTION

Paul Ehrlich formulated the targeted drug delivery systems to a diseased people.

Liposomes are vesicular structures composed of uni or multi layers surrounded by a equal number of aqueous compartment. Liposomes are composed of naturally derived phospholipids and cholesterol.

ADVANTAGES OF LIPOSOME'S:

- They are biocompatible, totally biodegradable, non-toxic, and immunogenic.
- Appropriate for delivery of hydrophobic, hydrophilic and amphipathic drugs.
- Keep the encapsulated medicine safe from the outside atmosphere.
- Reduced the toxicity and increased stability.
- Precise site target drug delivery.

DISADVANTAGES OF LIPOSOME'S:

- There is a problem with leaks.
- $t_{1/2}$ half life is short.
- At times phospholipids undergo oxidation and hydrolysis.
- cost is economic. Liposomes come in a variety of shapes and sizes. Liposomes are classed according on structural characteristics. Unilamellar vesicles are vesicles that have no lamellae.

MECHANISM OF LIPOSOME FORMATION

Phospholipids, which are amphiphilic molecules, make up the basic or important element of a liposome. The hydrophilic component is significant because it is mostly phosphoric acid coupled to a water-soluble molecule, whereas the hydrophobic part is made up of two fatty acid chains each with 10-24 carbon atoms and 0-6 double bonds. When these phospholipids are disseminated or spread in aqueous conditions, the polar head organizes to create lamellar sheets. group faces the aqueous area, while the fatty acid groups each other, resulting in liposomes, which are spherical/vesicle-like structures. The polar portion remains in contact or touch with the aqueous zone, while the non-polar half is shielded or kept safe. (13)

When phospholipids are hydrated in water, along with the input of energy like Sonication, shaking, heating, homogenization, etc. it is the hydrophilic/hydrophobic interfaces between lipid-lipid, lipid-water molecules that illustrate the formation of bilayer vesicles in way to reach the thermodynamic equilibrium in the aqueous phase. The main cause for bilayer setting up comprises:

1. Folding into tight concentric vesicles reduces the opposing cooperation between the hydrophilic and hydrophobic phases.
2. By assembling super molecular self-assembled structures into vesicles, maximum stability may be achieved.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Acyclovir was a kind gift from VRL pharma tech. India. Phosphatidylcholine (solid) and Cholesterol (CHOL) are used as excipients. All the excipients and Reagents were used as received of AR Grade. Distilled water was prepared freshly whenever needed.

PREFORMULATION STUDIES OF ACYCLOVIR

Extra amount of drug become taken in a five ml of the solvent gadget. Stir it for half-hour. Preserve it on a shaker for forty-eight hrs. to gain equilibrium and centrifuge it for 10 mins, the supernatant layer is then filtered out. The dilutions are crafted from 10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and the solubility is decided by means of measuring the UV absorption.

Determination of absorption maxima (λ_{max}) for acyclovir:

2 ml of stock solution (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was taken in 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to 10 ml with solutions of pH 7.4 PBS (20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and scanned on a double beam Spectrophotometer against respective media blanks. This λ_{max} was selected for preparation of standard curve of acyclovir different media.

FT-IR study

Dry sample of drug and potassium bromide was mixed uniformly and filled into the die cavity of Sample holder and an IR spectrum was recorded using diffuse reflectance FTIR Spectrophotometer

THIN FILM LIPID HYDRATION BY HANDSHAKING:

To create liposome lipid particles must be brought into a watery situation. At the point when dry lipid layer film is hydrated the lamellae expand and develop into myelin figures. Myelin figures rupture and reseal the exposed hydrophobic edges caused by mechanical disturbance such as vortexing, shaking, swirling, or pipetting, resulting in the arrangement of liposomes that may be generated by hand-shaken method. (12)

Formulation of liposome's by thin film lipid hydration method.

Formulation Code	Cholesterol (mg)	Phosphatidylcholine(mg)
F1	50mg	50mg
F2	50mg	100mg
F3	50mg	150mg
F4	50mg	250mg
F5	50mg	350mg
F6	50mg	550mg

SONICATION

Sonication is helpful the most extensively used method for the preparation of SUV. Under a passive environment, MLVs are sonicated with a bath type sonicator or a probe sonicator. The primary drawbacks of this approach are its low internal volume/encapsulation effectiveness, the possibility of phospholipids and chemicals to be encapsulated degrading, the removal of big molecules, metal contamination from the probe tip, and the existence of MLV alongside SUV. There are two Sonication techniques: Probe Sonication a sonicator's tip is inserted directly into the liposome dispersion. In this approach, the energy input into lipid dispersion is extremely high. Because the coupling of energy at the tip causes localized heat, the vessel must be immersed in a water/ice bath. More than 5% of the lipids can be deesterified during sonication for up to 1 hour. Titanium will also peel off and contaminate the solution while using the probe sonicator.

EVALUATION OF LIPOSOMES:

Liposomal formulation and processing for specified purpose are characterized to ensure their predictable in vitro and in vivo performance. The characterization parameters for purpose of evaluation could be classified into three broad categories which include physical, chemical and biological parameters. Size, shape, surface characteristics, lamellar, phase behavior, and drug release profile are all evaluated during physical characterization. Biological characterization qualities help in establishing the formulation's safety and acceptability for therapeutic use. Chemical characterization investigations include those that establish the purity and potency of various lipophilic ingredients. (2)

THE FOLLOWING ARE SOME OF THE PARAMETERS:

1. Vesicle shape and lamellarity:

Electron microscopic techniques can be used to determine vesicle shape. Freeze-Fracture Electron Microscopy and P-31 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Analysis are used to measure the lamellarity of vesicles, or the number of bilayers present in liposomes.

2. Size and size distribution of vesicles:

The literature mentions several ways for assessing size and size distribution. Light Microscopy, Fluorescent Microscopy, Electron Microscopy (especially Transmission Electron Microscopy), Laser light scattering Photon correlation Spectroscopy, Field Flow Fractionation, Gel Permeation, and Gel Exclusion are only a few of the techniques available. Because electron microscopy allows you to view each individual liposome and obtain exact information on the profile of the liposome population over a wide range of sizes, it is the most precise method for assessing liposome size. Unfortunately, it takes a long time and requires equipment that isn't always readily available. On the other hand, the laser light scattering method is simple and quick to employ, but it has the drawback of detecting the average property of the bulk of liposomes. All of these strategies necessitate the purchase of expensive equipment. Gel exclusion chromatography methods are recommended if just a rough concept of size range is required because the only expenditures are buffers and gel material.

Characterization of liposomes

Drug entrapment efficiency (or) drug content:(1)

Entrapment efficiency of liposomes was determined by centrifugation method. Aliquots of liposomal dispersion were subjected to centrifugation on a laboratory centrifuge (Remi R4C) at 3500 rpm for a period of 90 min. To separate non-entrapped medicines, the clear supernatants were carefully removed, and absorbance was measured at 252 nm. The debris in the centrifuge tube (100 ml) was diluted with phosphate buffer pH 7, and the absorbance of this solution was measured at 252 nm. The total amount of drug in the dispersion was calculated by adding the drug amounts in the supernatant and sediment. (5).

% Entrapment of drug was calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Entrapment efficiency (\%)} = ((\text{Total amount of the drug} - \text{amount of the free drug}) / \text{Total drug}) \times 100.$$

In vitro diffusion studies:

In-vitro release studies were performed using modified Franz diffusion cells. Between the receptor and donor compartments, a dialysis membrane (HI Media molecular weight 5000) was inserted. Acyclovir liposomal suspension was placed in the donor compartment, and the receptor compartment was filled with phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (18 ml). The diffusion cells were maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C with stirring at 300 rpm throughout the experiment. 2 ml of aliquots were extracted at predetermined intervals and examined using a UV Spectrophotometer at 250 nm. Data obtained from in-vitro release studies were fitted to various kinetic equations to find out the mechanism of acyclovir release from liposomal suspension.

C. Dialysis membrane was taken and one end of the membrane was sealed. After separation of non-entrapped acyclovir liposome dispersion was filled in the dialysis membrane and other end was closed. The dialysis membrane containing the sample was suspended in the medium. The assay process was done by withdrawing 1 ml of sample at regular intervals for 12 hours and immediately replaced by the same quantity of buffer in to the donor component. The received samples were assayed by UV spectrophotometer at 250 nm.

Particle size analysis:

The particle size of liposomes was determined by using scanning electron microscope. Optimized batch of liposomes were viewed under microscope to study their size. Size of liposomal vesicles was measured at different locations on slide by taking a small drop of liposomal dispersion on it and average size of liposomal vesicles was determined.

Zeta potential

This method is used to determine charge on empty and drug loaded vesicles surface using Zetasizer 300HSA (Malvern instruments, Malvern UK). Analysis time was kept for 60 seconds and average zeta potential and charge on the liposome was determined. The obtained value indicates that the surface of liposomes is dominated by the anions and proved that liposome have sufficient charge to avoid aggregation of vesicles.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Solubility profile of Acyclovir.

S. No.	Solvent	Solubility
1	Distilled water	Slightly soluble
2	Dil. Hydrochloric acid	Soluble
3	Dil. Sodium hydroxide	Sparingly soluble
4	Methanol	Sparingly soluble

Determination of absorption maxima (λ_{max}) for acyclovir

Preparation of 0.1N HCL solution: 85 ml of hydrochloric acid is made upto 1000 ml to attain 0.1N HCL. Preparation of acyclovir stock solution: 10 mg of acyclovir drug is dissolved in 100 ml of 0.1 N HCL solution to obtain (100 μ g/ml). For the 100 μ g/ml conc, determine the absorption maxima observed at 250nm.

From the stock solution of 100 μ g/ml take different concentrations and make dilution with 0.1 N HCL solutions. Different concentrations like 0.5,1,2,3,4 and 5 ml solution were taken and diluted to 10 ml to obtain different concentrations 5 μ g/ml,10 μ g/ml,20 μ g/ml,30 μ g/ml,40 μ g/ml,50 μ g/ml determine the absorbance of solutions.

Figure 1.0 Absorption maxima of acyclovir drug.

Figure 1.1 Calibration curve of acyclovir drug.

TABLE:ZETAPOTENTIAL AND GLOBULAR SIZE VALUES

SO. NO	FORMULATION RATIO	GLOBULAR SIZE (nm)	ZETA POTENTIAL (mv)
F1	1:1	527nm	-33.5mv
F2	2:1	382nm	-20mv
F3	3:1	312nm	-10mv
F4	5:1	362nm	-13.8mv
F5	7:1	284nm	-6.7mv
F6	11:1	147nm	-6.3mv

Graphs of formulation 6 zetapotential and globule size

FTIR GRAPHS

Figure 2.1 Ftir graph of Acyclovir drug.

Figure 2.2 Ftir graph of drug and excipient mixture.

Comparisons of spectra of Acyclovir along with the physical mixture shows the absence of interaction and presence of drug in unchanged form.

Drug entrapment efficiency or drug content and entrapment efficiency.

S.no	Formulation ratio	Drug entrapment	% entrapment efficiency
1	F1 1:1	7.8±0.01	78%
2	F2 2:1	8.1±0.02	81%
3	F3 3:1	8.5±0.02	85%
4	F4 5:1	9.0±0.02	90%
5	F5 7:1	9.2±0.04	92%
6	F6 11:1	9.6±0.05	96%

In-vitro drug release of Acyclovir Liposomes

Time(hr)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	5.09	3.96	4.95	3.66	3.6	2.36
1	10.49	7.1	10.15	8.14	6.19	5.73
1.5	14.23	11.61	15.97	12.14	7.95	8.26
2	17.63	13.45	19.07	15.45	12.81	11.75
2.5	34.41	32.42	36.1	29.25	19.16	18.11
3	54.18	41.27	41.18	39.98	27.79	26.61
4	68.96	58.09	52.2	49.94	39.72	34.27
5	77.58	67.27	63.38	56.27	53.3	44.71
6	-	80.82	75.06	69.95	65.04	58.26
7	-	-	84.53	80.7	75.3	62.97
8	-	-	-	89.12	83.16	74.8
9	-	-	-	-	89.71	87.3
10	-	-	-	-	91.31	92.15
11	-	-	-	-	-	95.98

Cumulative percentage drug release of Acyclovir Liposome formulations F1-F6.

Formulation F₁ containing cholesterol and phosphatidylcholine in the ratio of 1:1 had % cumulative release of 78% in 12 hours respectively. When the concentration increases which shows the cholesterol and phosphatidyl choline helpful in retarding the drug release. Formulation F₂ containing cholesterol and phosphatidyl choline in the ratios of 1:2 had % cumulative release of 81 % respectively which shows that the drug released in controlled manner. Formulation F₃ containing cholesterol and phosphatidyl choline in the ratio of 1:3 had % cumulative drug release of 85% in 12 hours respectively. Formulation F₄ containing cholesterol and phosphatidyl choline in the ratios of 1:5 had 90% cumulative drug release of in 12 hrs respectively. Formulation F₅ containing cholesterol and phosphatidyl choline 1:7 had % cumulative drug release 92%. It also observes that cumulative drug release increases when concentration of cholesterol and phosphatidyl choline was increased. Formulation F₆ has cholesterol and lecithin (11:1) which has shown highest % cumulative drug release up to 96%.

Figure 3.1: Images of liposomes at different ratios in 40x microscope.

CONCLUSION

The different formulations of liposomes containing acyclovir were prepared by using thin film lipid hydration by hand shake method. The maximum entrapment efficiency was judged to be 96 percent, and the percentage entrapment efficiency was determined to be 96 percent. These formulations are found to have good entrapment efficiency and it was proved that as the concentration of cholesterol was decreased and increased concentration of phosphatidyl choline and particle size decreased in globules and entrapment efficiency was enhanced. The ratio of phosphatidylcholine and cholesterol is 11:1 is selected as the best formulation based on entrapment efficient and diffusion studies. From the above research concluded that acyclovir can be formulated as liposomes with phospholipids and cholesterol for better drug release and enhanced permeability, Recommend future Research.

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